

Novel Multiband Orientation-Insensitive FSS Based on Dipole for Chipless RFID

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Abstract— In this paper, a new FSS unit cell geometry is presented. Pairs of vertical and horizontal slot dipoles are used to create an orientation-insensitive multiband pass frequency response. The proposed structure operates in the C-band (4-6 GHz) and X-band (8-12GHz) and presents ten resonant frequencies. Since each passband is independent, this geometry is suited for application as chipless orientation-insensitive RFID tags. The S_{21} simulation results are present and were carried out by CST Microwave Studio.

Keywords—*Frequency Selective Surface; chipless RFID; UWB FSS;*

I. INTRODUCTION

FSSs (Frequency Selective Surfaces) are two-dimensional periodic arrays of elements that behave as spatial filters to electromagnetic waves [1]. They have been drawing attention from the scientific community due to the frequency filtering properties. These features make the FSS appropriate for a number of applications. At microwave wavelengths, FSS is low manufacturing cost, low weight, easy to manufacture and presents high integration with other microwave circuits. The FSS behaves as a stopband if the single element of the array is a patch or a passband if the element is a slot [2]. The resonant frequency depends on the periodicity, incident angle, dielectric properties and geometry of the elements [3]. The shape of the elements can be a combination of patches and slots. Various geometries can be used to form an FSS element as dipole, cross dipole, Jerusalem cross, circular, square and hexagonal loops [4].

The design of multiband FSS has attracted attention because of the increasing demands on multi-functionality of devices for communications [5]. To design a multiband frequency response there are many methods such as fractal elements [6, 7], combined elements [8] and multilayered FSS [9]. Typical applications of FSSs are millimeter-wave spacial filters, artificial magnetic conductors, radomes, antenna reflectors and absorbers [10].

Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) system is a wireless technology which uses RF waves to read an encoded data remotely. The RFID technology is composed by an RFID tag, where data is encoded, and a RFID reader used to extract the encoded data from the tags. Typically, RFID tags contain a chip: a microcontroller to perform simple functions such as controlling serial data transmission. Because of this feature, RFIDs are expensive when compared to optical barcodes.

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However, chipless printable RFID tags can be a cost-efficient alternative to traditional RFIDs [11], as depicted by this paper.

The authors propose a multiband FSS that can be used as chipless RFID tags. The information can be encoded in the resonant frequencies, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The FSS implemented here presents ten resonant frequencies and is insensitive oriented due to the symmetry of the geometry. Each passband represents a bit and the characteristic of dual polarization doubles the encoding capacity of the tags. The simulations were carried out by CST Microwave Studio.

Fig. 1. Basic principles of a chipless RFID technology with FSS [11].

II. FSS DESIGN

A. Principle of operation

In a traditional RFID solution, the RFID tag remains inoperative until it is hit by an interrogation signal. This wave also provides power for the built-in chip, that proceeds to send back a signal that contains encoded information.

The chipless RFID uses the reflecting properties of an FSS to encode information. When an electromagnetic wave hits a FSS, portions of the incident wave can be reflected, transmitted or absorbed. Instead of being stored in a chip, the information is encoded into the FSS's frequency response. In particular, its resonant frequencies can be used for this task. The interrogation signal must therefore be a UWB signal. The reflected can be analyzed (via Fourier's Transform or filtering) to recover the encoded information.

Since the frequency response is a function of the unit cell geometry, the tag does not require the use of chips, therefore

significantly reducing the tag cost. A drawback is the requirement of UWB transmitters and receivers.

B. Proposed chipless RFID tag

In this paper, the FSS unit cell is composed by a collection of pairs of slot dipoles (Fig. 2). The typical response of the dipole is independent of the incident wave's polarity due to the symmetry of the geometry. Since the unit cell of slot type, the frequency response behaves as a band-pass spatial filter.

Fig. 2. FSS chipless RFID tag unit cell.

Each slot dipole is responsible for a resonant frequency, and consequently, a transmitted band appears on the FSS's frequency response. By shorting one pair of dipoles (filling its slot with metal), the frequencies are then reflected. The reflection/transmission of the incident wave can then be used to encode one bit of information. Every dipole ($A_1 \dots A_{10}$) possesses a fixed width W , length ($L_1 \dots L_{10}$) and separation ($g_{1-2} \dots g_{9-10}$). The dual polarization doubles the encoding capacity of the tags.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The proposed FSS is designed on FR-4 substrate (dielectric constant = 4.5; loss tangent = 0.032 and thickness = 0.1mm). For industrial applications, the device can be fabricated by depositing conductive ink on paper or plastic product packing. The FSS presents 10 pass-bands from 4 to 13 GHz.

A. Simulated Results

Figs. 3-5 show the simulated S_{21} results for some variations of the FSS's unit cell. Fig. 3 presents the frequency response for the structure composed of all 10 dipoles for vertical (Full-Vr) and horizontal (Full-Hr) incident waves. As the results present 10 resonant frequencies, each slot dipole is responsible for a passband. One can notice also that the structure is insensitive for vertical and horizontal polarization.

Fig. 3. Frequency response for the FSS chipless RFID tag with 10 dipoles.

Table I shows some characteristics of the slot dipoles. The fixed width W is 0.4 mm and gap between the dipoles are: $g_{1-2} = g_{2-3} = \dots = g_{7-8} = 1.5\text{mm}$ and $g_{8-9} = g_{9-10} = 1\text{mm}$. These distances were determined by simulation in order to minimize coupling between adjacent dipoles.

TABLE I. CHARACTERISTICS OF SLOT DIPOLES

	Parameter	
	Length (mm)	Resonant Frequency (GHz)
A_1	25	4.72
A_2	22.25	5.34
A_3	19.80	6
A_4	17.62	6.73
A_5	15.68	7.48
A_6	13.96	8.32
A_7	12.42	9.37
A_8	11.05	10.27
A_9	9.84	11.37
A_{10}	8.66	12.68

At the resonant frequencies of the table 1, S_{21} above -10 dB is considered 1 bit and below is considered 0 bit. Thus, by removing one, or more dipoles, the resonant frequency related to that slot dipole disappears. In this case, S_{21} is below -10 dB and the bit is 0.

Fig. 4 shows the S_{21} results for the FSS chipless RFID tag for two examples for sequence of bits. Fig. 4 (a) and Fig. 4(b) show S_{21} results when only the even (01010101) slot and odd (10101010) slot dipoles are kept, respectively. For a comparison, Fig. 5 shows the frequency responses for even (Even-Hr) and odd (Odd-Hr) dipoles, both on horizontal and vertical polarization. By these results, one can infer that the removal of a slot dipole does not significantly shift the other resonant frequencies related to the adjacent slot dipoles. Thus, the presence and absence of dipole can form different tags easily differentiated from each other.

(a) – Frequency response when keeping the even dipoles

(b) – Frequency response when keeping the odd dipoles

Fig. 4. Frequency response for the FSS chipless RFID tag when shorting some slot dipoles.

Fig. 5. Frequency response for the FSS chipless RFID tag comparing even and odd slot dipoles.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper was presented a new FSS unit cell geometry using a collection of vertically and horizontally oriented slot dipoles for application as chipless orientation-insensitive RFID tags. Simulated results show that the proposed structure allows for freedom in the design of the multi passband structure representing 10 bits (denoted by slot dipoles' resonant frequencies) with minimum coupling between adjacent dipoles. The FSS chipless RFID tag operates in the C-band (4 - 6 GHz) and X-band (8-12 GHz). The presence (bit 1) and absence (bit 0) of dipole can form different tags easily differentiated from each other. Thus, this structure shows strong potential for application in passive RFID tags.

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